

Metamorphosing of Speckled Leukoplakia Into Carcinoma - A Review

Dr. Gurleen Kaur Sandhu,
B.D.S
gurleen.sandhu01@gmail.com

Abstract

Potentially malignant conditions precede malignancies. Oral squamous cell carcinoma has several antecedents, including leukoplakia. One of the leukoplakia varieties that usually develop into cancer is speckled leukoplakia. A significant diagnostic and therapeutic difficulty is posed by speckled leukoplakia. We have described a case of speckled leukoplakia on the right side of the buccal mucosa that developed into cancer in situ along with a review of the literature in light of recent findings. We also made an effort to discuss the clinical significance and treatment options available for the condition.

Key Words: Malignancies, potentially malignant disorders, speckled leukoplakia, Carcinoma

Introduction

The general public is becoming more aware of lesions in the oral cavity that may be cancerous. Leukoplakia is a oral cavity lesion that has been discovered. The term "leukoplakia" comes from Greek words "plakia," which means plaques or patches and "leuko" which means white. Leukoplakia is therefore described as a white plaque that cannot be removed by scraping. However, even after removing all risk variables with no inclination toward malignancy, still its origin remains unclear^[1]. Leukoplakia is a lesion that affects around 3% of people globally, and 5-25% of cases are pre-malignant lesions. All leukoplakia lesions might be taken into consideration as possible malignant lesions if confirmed by histological analysis.^[2] The term Speckled Leukoplakia (SL), which was used by the World Health Organization (WHO) is now used to refer to the existence of both white and red areas on the oral mucosa.^[3] Speckled leukoplakia instances in India are quite rare. This case report describes a case of speckled leukoplakia that affected the right side of the buccal mucosa and reached the alveolar area. With a high probability of malignant transformation and a precursor lesion of squamous cell carcinoma, SL is an uncommon and extremely aggressive clinicopathological condition.

Case Report

A 58-year-old man who had a white spot on his buccal mucosa came to the clinic. The white area, whose steady development caused

discomfort and a burning sensation, was initially detected one year ago. He had been a smoker since he was about 29 years old, but he hasn't smoked in over 5 years. Additionally, he had been chewing raw tobacco two to three times a day for the past ten years. The patient also occasionally drank beer in addition to these. The right buccal mucosa underwent intraoral examination which revealed 2 × 2 cm red and white patches that were firm, non-tender, and non-scratchable. [Fig.1] The surface seemed uneven and somewhat raised, clinically resembling speckled leukoplakia. Red splotchy spots were intermingled with the lesion. To choose the location for the biopsy, toluidine blue staining was done while the patient was in the chair. The chosen region was then biopsied (incision). [Fig.2] Squamous epithelium covering connective tissue stroma was seen during histopathologic investigation using H and E-stained sections. The epithelium displayed dysplastic characteristics such as wide rete ridges, acanthosis, hyperchromatism, basilar hyperplasia, cellular and nuclear pleomorphism, aberrant mitosis, individual cell keratinization and production of intraepithelial keratin pearls. Top to bottom, dysplastic epithelial alterations were seen. The stroma of connective tissue was highly cellular and contained numerous chronically inflamed cells as well as dilated and thriving capillaries. [Fig:3,4,5] The transformation of speckled leukoplakia into cancer in situ was determined to be diagnosed on the basis of overall clinical and histological findings.

Figure 1: Showing speckled leukoplakia in right side of buccal mucosa.

Figure 2: Grossing image showing tissue of incisional biopsy.

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5: Histopathology showing Speckled leukoplakia transforming into Carcinoma in situ [H & E X10]

Discussion

According to the World Health Organization, leukoplakia is a white patch or plaque that cannot be diagnosed as any other disease, either clinically or pathologically and is only caused by smoking. No other physical or chemical agents are known to cause leukoplakia.^[5] However, the research makes a compelling case for the involvement of viruses, alcohol, and underlying health issues. The occurrence of both white and red patches on the oral mucosa is known as speckled leukoplakia (SL) according to the World Health Organization (WHO).^[6] Homogeneous and non-homogeneous leukoplakia are the two primary clinical kinds of leukoplakia. Non-homogenous leukoplakia is the term used to describe speckled leukoplakia.

The etiology of cancer is influenced by several variables, including the consumption of alcohol and cigarettes, diets low in antioxidants (such as vitamins C, E, and beta-carotene), occupational exposure to carcinogens, viral infections, genetic and hereditary factors, and others. The usage of tobacco products was shown to be the most potent independent risk factor. An additional list of contributory variables included hyperacidity, lipstick, ill-fitting dentures, and other tobacco products, highlighting the influence of socioeconomic status and way of life on the emergence of premalignant lesions.^[7] Several names have been used to describe the presence of both white and red patches. Lesions known as erythroplakia are completely red. SL is indicated by red and white patches on the mucosa.^[4] The chance of speckled leukoplakia turning malignant is greater than that of other varieties. Therefore, early detection by biopsy is necessary to prevent potentially deadly malignant transformation.^[8] Approximately 80% of SL eventually develop into oral

carcinoma over time, despite a range of therapies. Contrastingly, 5–10% of homogeneous leukoplakia will develop into a carcinoma.^[4] SL is resistant to the majority of existing therapeutic options, including surgery^[4]. Therefore, complete excision with unrestricted surgical margins and lifetime monitoring is essential. Leukoplakia has a greater malignant potential in women (6%) than in males (3.9%). Compared to ordinary leukoplakia, those linked with tobacco chewing have a greater risk of malignant transformation^[7]. In the commissure area and buccal mucosa malignant transformation can occur in 1.8 percent of cases. Malignant transformation have been found in the area of the lip and tongue in 16–38% of cases. It has been shown that the yearly malignant transformation rate ranges from 0.1% to 17%.^[9]

Management

When determining the type of treatment for the patient, the degree of epithelial dysplasia is crucial. Two risk groups were identified by Martorell Calatayud^[10] along with the ensuing therapeutic options:

Group 1: Individuals with minimal malignancy risk, those homogeneous leukoplakias that appear clinically as leukoplakias without dysplasia, those in low-risk locations that exhibit minor dysplasia, those with a thickness of less than 200 mm, etc. In this group, a variety of therapy modalities can be used as treatment of lesions using topical or oral retinoids, such as 1.5–2 mg/kg body weight for three months of 13-Cis-Retinoic Acid 10 mg treatments utilizing non-surgical ablative methods, such as carbon dioxide laser ablation and cryotherapy. In this low-risk category, laser light therapy is seen to be the best option since it has shown superior outcomes in terms of managing the lesions.

Group 2:

Those who are at a high risk of developing cancer, which includes: Leukoplakias with mild dysplasia that are present in high-risk areas and measure more than 200 mm or those linked to a nonhomogeneous clinical form; Leukoplakias with moderate or severe dysplasia and Verrucous leukoplakias. The aggressive surgical approach of removing the full thickness of the mucosa at the leukoplakia site is advised for this group of patients. This is comparable to the current situation. Although there are numerous alternative treatments available, avoiding risk factors (such as smoking and drinking) and etiological factors (such as sharp fractured teeth, defective metal restorations, and metal bridges) are a preventative approach that could be used on all patients with these lesions.^[8] Both in treated and untreated patients, routine check-ups of these individuals are crucial, likely every 3, 6 and eventually 12 months.

Conclusion

Speckled leukoplakia is a condition in patients that might be cancerous. Any potentially cancerous condition should be actively addressed. Early diagnosis is crucial for both treatment and prognosis of speckled leukoplakia due to the high malignant transformation rate of this condition.

References

1. Kardam P, Rehani S, Mehendiratta M, Sahay K, Mathias Y, Sharma R. Journey of leukoplakia so far - an insight on shortcomings of definitions and classifications. *J Dent Oral Disord Ther.* 2015; 3(2):1-6.
2. Linggen MW. Head and neck. In: Kumar V, Abbas AK, Aster, JC. editors. *Robbins and cotran-pathologic basis of disease.* 9th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2015. p. 731.
3. Barnes L, Eveson JW, Reichart P, Sidransky D (Eds): *World Health Organization Classification of Tumors. Pathology and Genetics of Head and Neck Tumours.* IARC Press. Lyon 2005.
4. Scully C. Oral Leukoplakia. [eMedicine web site]. October 2008. Accessed October 30, 2009.
5. Pindborg J.J., Reichart P., Smith C.J., and Van der Waal I. *World Health Organization: histological typing of cancer and precancer of the oral mucosa.* Berlin: Springer-Verlag; 1997.
6. Eversole LR. Dysplasia of the Upper Aerodigestive Tract Squamous Epithelium. *Head and Neck Pathol.* 2009; 3:63-8.
7. Reibel J. Prognosis of oral premalignant lesions: significance of clinical, histopathological, and molecular biological characteristics. *Critical Reviews in Oral Biology and Medicine* 2003; 14(1):47-62.
8. Scuba J.J. Oral leukoplakia. *Critical Rev Oral Biol Med* 1995;(2):147-160.
9. Lodi G. and Porter S. Management of potentially malignant disorders: evidence and critique. *Journal of Oral Pathology and Medicine* 2008; 37(2), 63-69.
10. Martorell-Calatayud,a R. Botella- Estrada,a J.V. Bagán-Sebastián,b O. Sanmartín-Jiménez,a and Guillén- Baróna C. Oral Leukoplakia: Clinical, Histopathologic, and Molecular Features and Therapeutic Approach. *Acta Dermosifiliogr.* 2009; 100:669-84.
11. Scuba J.J. Oral leukoplakia. *Critical Rev Oral Biol Med* 1995;(2):147-160.